

Supplemental Materials for Subspace modeling enabled high-sensitivity X-ray chemical imaging

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Contents

A Overview of the contributions	1
B Analysis of the proposed algorithm	2
B.1. SURE-based Parameter Selection	2
B.2. Selection of the off-the-shelf Gaussian denoiser	3
B.3. Effect on the data sampling rate.	3
B.4. Motion robustness	4
B.5. Limitations of The Proposed Method	5
C Experimental results	5
C.1. Details of the test datasets	5
C.2. Comparison to denoising individual frames	6
C.3. More comparison results	6
C.4. Results of real dataset	12

A. Overview of the contributions

Synchrotrons use electricity to produce intense X-rays that span a broad spectrum. When X-rays interact with an atom or molecule, a variety of signals can result, depending on the type of atom and its chemical environment [8]. The ability to tune the energy of the incident photons with high resolution opens the vast field of XAS imaging. The applications of X-ray chemical XAS imaging include dual-energy contrast imaging techniques [11], in which images directly below and above the absorption edge of a specific chemical element of interest are recorded, as well as the full-field TXM-XANES imaging [23, 32], in which a stack of images is obtained at different energies, generating an absorption spectrum (XANES spectrum) for each pixel within the field of view. These spectra are further fit with known reference compounds using a least-square fitting method to determine the edge energy position. The resulting chemical phases for each pixel can be represented as a two-dimensional color map. The concept of TXM-XANES imaging technique is illustrated in Fig. 1. Together with the capability of rotating the sample stage in TXM, the collection of multiple two-dimensional chemical maps at different angles allows tomographic reconstruction with three-dimensional chemical speciation. To handle the system imperfections and speed up the acquisition time, 3D median filtering is often used to improve the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the TXM-XANES imaging data [15, 23]. Clustering of spectra and then averaging are also proposed to improve the SNR [28]. The improvement of these approaches, however, is marginal especially for high-noise cases. The clustering approach also reduces the spatial resolution of the chemical map, which is suboptimal for high-resolution analysis.

There have been tremendous efforts over the years in developing better (both traditional and machine-learning-based) image restoration algorithms in imaging science. They have been demonstrated to be effective in natural camera [6, 9, 21, 26, 34], fluorescence microscopy [7, 12, 14, 17, 33, 36], electron microscopy [5, 29], super-resolution microscopy [24] and synchrotron X-ray tomography [16], etc. A specific requirement for its application in TXM-XANES imaging is that

Figure 1. (a) Principles of the TXM-XANES imaging technique. A monochromatic X-ray beam is focused onto the sample using the condenser and the image is projected onto the detector. One image is acquired in absorption contrast at each energy and the XANES spectrum is reconstructed from a series of images with multiple energy points. The normalized XANES spectra are subsequently fitted to create a chemical phase map, representing the chemical states transformation. (b) The proposed approach (SUM) significantly improves the signal-to-noise ratio of the projection images, which enables much faster data acquisition. (c) It also preserves the spectrum information for a single representative pixel, which is indicated as a blue dot in (b). (d) The fitted chemical phase map after denoising has a substantially higher correlation with the ground truth in (a).

the algorithm has to be effective and scalable to large datasets. Indeed, in a typical study with TXM-XANES [28], two-dimensional XANES images can have image size 1024×1024 pixels (after binning of 2) which cover a field of view of about 16.4×16.4 μm . As reported, data was collected from 288 energy points across the absorption K-edge of Ni from 8100 eV to 9022 eV, which took ~ 2.5 hours. The acquisition time of three-dimensional measurements is even longer (~ 60 hours) resulting in a dataset with size over 500Gb.

The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- We propose a simple and robust denoising algorithm (SUM) for low-exposure measurements of TXM-XANES data to accelerate the imaging speed and improve the chemical-resolvability.
- The SUM algorithm is formulated into an optimization framework. There are no hyperparameters that need to be tuned.
- We quantitatively and qualitatively evaluate the proposed algorithm on synthetic and real datasets and show that it performs favorably against other approaches in terms of accuracy and processing speed.

We would like to point out that another direction of our future work is to adaptively select the energy points to further reduce the acquisition time and enable efficient autonomous experiments [25]. Moreover, the proposed algorithm is not limited to X-ray imaging. Multispectral image restoration could be another suitable application.

B. Analysis of the proposed algorithm

B.1. SURE-based Parameter Selection

The proposed algorithm is simple and effective to improve the quality of TXM-XANES imaging data. However, the size of the low-dimensional subspace K is a critical parameter to achieving optimal performance. Too many components result in poor representations while too few lead to large variances. To find the correct trade-off K for the proposed algorithm

Figure 2. **Automatic hyperparameter determination.** (a) The optimal thresholding singular value (δ) is determined by minimizing the mean squared error (MSE) and its unbiased estimate (SURE). (b) Demonstration of the effect of different δ 's in (a) on the obtained spectrum by the proposed denoising algorithm. Over-estimated δ leads to over-smoothed spectrum, while under-estimated δ gives noisy spectrum.

$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \mathcal{F}_K(\mathbf{y})$, we revisit that our essential goal is to minimize the mean squared error (MSE) between the estimate $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ and ground truth \mathbf{x} , that is to minimize $\text{MSE}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{MNT} \mathbb{E} \{ \|\mathcal{F}_K(\mathbf{y}) - \mathbf{x}\|^2 \}$. In practice, \mathbf{x} is unknown but MSE can be well approximated by the Stein's unbiased risk estimate (SURE) [31], which is only related to the observation \mathbf{y} . Thus instead of optimizing the MSE, in which the ground truth is unknown, we can directly minimize the SURE to determine the optimal parameter. The formula and derivation procedure of SURE is similar to those of other works [6, 14, 18], thus omit here. As shown in Fig. 2, the optimal thresholding values obtained by MSE and SURE minimization are identical.

B.2. Selection of the off-the-shelf Gaussian denoiser

The flexibility of the proposed algorithm allows us to plug-in any kinds of state-of-the-art *image* denoising approaches. Here we focus on two representative algorithms: BM3D [9] and DnCNN [35]. As shown in Fig. 3, both methods can significantly improve the PSNRs and correlations under different conditions, while SUM with BM3D obtains slightly better results. However, the running time of SUM with DnCNN is much smaller than the other, especially when the data size is large. The part of reason is that DnCNN benefits from GPU computation while the implementation of BM3D is on CPU only. We adopt the DnCNN for the following experiments. Note that naively applying these methods to individual frames is undesirable (see Section C).

B.3. Effect on the data sampling rate.

Even if the proposed denoising approach is initially aiming at reducing the exposure time, it turns out that it also helps minimize the number of energy points for a reasonably good chemical map. As shown in Fig. 4, we apply the SUM algorithm to the reduced-sampling-rate data and calculate the correlation with the ground truth under different noise conditions. The energy points are randomly selected. The results show that in order to get over 0.8 correlation, only 10% data is needed if the noise is small, and 40% data is needed if the noise is large, with the help of denoising.

	$\sigma = 10$			$\sigma = 150$		
	Small	Medium	Large	Small	Medium	Large
Noisy	0.63	0.58	0.54	0.04	0.04	0.04
MedFilt3	0.69	0.65	0.67	0.07	0.04	0.04
SVD	0.77	0.71	0.67	0.31	0.31	0.22
ReLD	0.79	0.75	0.72	0.06	0.08	0.07
VBM4D	0.77	0.71	0.70	0.15	0.17	0.16
SUM	0.84	0.78	0.78	0.76	0.72	0.72

Table 1. **Demonstration of robustness to jitter motion.** The correlation coefficients between the ground truth and calculated chemical maps obtained from various algorithms under different noise levels ($\sigma = 10$ and 150) and jitter amplitudes (small, medium and large). The best results within a 0.3 margin are shown in boldface.

Figure 3. **Selection of the off-the-shelf denoiser in SUM.** Two typical algorithms (BM3D and DnCNN) are evaluated in terms of frame PSNR (a), spectrum PSNR (b), correlation to chemical map (c) and running time (d).

Figure 4. **Denoising helps reduce the sampling percentage.** The correlation of the chemical maps obtained from the proposed algorithm SUM and the ground truth with respect to different sampling percentages. SUM has the potential to reduce the number of energy points.

B.4. Motion robustness

It should be noted that, because zone plate focusing is energy dependent, zone plate refocusing is performed for each energy and may result in jitter motion owing to poor motor precision. To evaluate the robustness of denoising algorithms

Figure 5. **Comparison of the chemical phase maps under different noise conditions.** The correlation coefficients to the ROI of the ground truth chemical phase map (left) are shown below the maps obtained from different algorithms. The proposed algorithm SUM produces highly accurate chemical phase maps.

Figure 6. **SUM helps jitter correction.** The averaged images of the motion-corrected noisy input and denoised output by SUM across energies under low noise (a) and high noise (b) conditions, respectively. Structural details are clearly preserved after denoising, which indicates the image sequences are well-aligned.

to jitter motion, we simulate the data with random motion at different levels (*Small*, *Medium* and *Large*), which are corresponding to jitter amplitudes 2, 4 and 6 pixels respectively. The motion correction is performed by NoRMCorre [27] before calculating the chemical phase map. As shown in Tab. 1, the SUM algorithm consistently outperforms other approaches often by a significant margin, which demonstrates the robustness of the proposed denoising approach.

Moreover, as shown in Fig. 6, compared with the motion correction on raw noisy data, the denoising helps correct the jitter motion as well. The averaged images after denoising show clearer structural details. This is another important application of the proposed denoising algorithm for X-ray imaging in practice.

B.5. Limitations of The Proposed Method

Memory Issue. The standard SVD calculation in the proposed approach may be not efficient for extremely large matrix (e.g. full resolution TXM images and thousands of energy points) that cannot fit into the computer’s main memory. This limitation can be addressed by applying randomized numerical linear algebra [10, 22].

Noise Assumption. We assume the noise distribution of X-ray images is Gaussian and additive. Though well approximated by Gaussian noise in many cases, more complicated noise types, such as mixed Poisson-Gaussian noise, should be considered in the extremely low-dosage situations. The variance stabilization transformation [20] or a new unbiased estimate considering the noise statistics [17] could be vital to addressing this limitation.

C. Experimental results

C.1. Details of the test datasets

Six different datasets, including X-ray projection images (*Particle*, *Catalyst* and *Round*) and reconstructed slices (*Electrode*, *Wedge* and *Brine*), are evaluated. The image size and sources are listed below:

- **Particle:** Image size, 190×260 . Pixel size, 35nm. Battery NCM particle [13]

- **Catalyst:** Image size, 2048×2448 . Pixel size, 22.3nm. PGM-fPt group metal free (PGM-free) catalyst [4].
- **Electrode:** Image size, 1137×1137 . Pixel size, 22.3nm. PGM-free electrode [1].
- **Wedge:** Image size, 1193×1193 . Pixel size, 23.2nm. Electrode made of lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC) particles surrounded by binder [3].
- **Round:** Image size, 2048×1792 . Pixel size, $0.7\mu\text{m}$. Shale samples [2].
- **Brine:** Image size, 742×761 . Pixel size, $1.64\mu\text{m}$. Sedimentary rock [30].

C.2. Comparison to denoising individual frames

We compare the proposed approach with denoising individual frame with the typical state-of-the-art image denoising algorithms (BM3D [9], DnCNN [35]). All results have shown significant improvement by considering the temporal information (information from cross-energy frames).

FPSNR (dB)					SPSNR (dB)				
α	Noisy	SUM	BM3D	DnCNN	α	Noisy	SUM	BM3D	DnCNN
30	18.59	44.30	34.74	18.96	30	8.19	19.82	13.29	8.26
90	9.05	38.94	29.87	9.35	90	6.74	16.24	11.28	6.75
120	6.55	37.18	28.33	6.85	120	6.50	15.00	10.75	6.50
150	4.61	36.06	27.04	4.91	150	6.38	14.79	10.36	6.37
Correlation					Running time (sec)				
α	Noisy	SUM	BM3D	DnCNN	α	SUM	BM3D	DnCNN	
30	0.29	0.98	0.87	0.30	30	3.34	178.29	5.60	
90	0.07	0.96	0.53	0.08	90	3.32	174.91	5.16	
120	0.04	0.95	0.36	0.06	120	4.33	178.40	5.25	
150	0.03	0.94	0.31	0.05	150	3.68	176.65	4.99	

Table 2. **Denoising results under different conditions in terms of FPSNR, SPSNR, Correlation and Running time.** Performance values are averaged and the proposed approach shows consistent improvement over denoising individual frames with BM3D and DnCNN.

C.3. More comparison results

Here we show the comparison of the proposed method with other two algorithms (BM4D [19] and SVD). They are showing relatively good results in our cases compared with other video denoising algorithms (as shown in Tab.1 in the main manuscript). The proposed SUM algorithm consistently achieves better results than other approaches and is very robust to a wide range of noise levels.

Figure 7. **Visual results of *Particle* under different noise conditions.** Comparison between the proposed algorithm SUM with the denoising with individual frames with BM3D and DnCNN. (a) Frame 700th; (b) Chemical map.

Figure 8. Visual comparison of *Electrode* with various methods under different noise conditions. (a) Frame 700th; (b) Chemical map.

Figure 9. Visual comparison of *Catalyst* with various methods under different noise conditions. (a) Frame 700th; (b) Chemical map.

Figure 10. Visual comparison of *Round* with various methods under different noise conditions. (a) Frame 700th; (b) Chemical map.

Figure 11. Visual comparison of *Brine* with various methods under different noise conditions. (a) Frame 700th; (b) Chemical map.

Particle					Electrode				
alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD	alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD
30	18.59	44.30	36.96	37.42	30	18.59	40.07	31.01	39.12
90	9.05	38.91	32.01	27.03	90	9.05	36.37	24.69	28.03
120	6.55	37.27	30.38	26.07	120	6.55	34.84	23.83	27.60
150	4.61	36.06	28.98	23.13	150	4.61	33.49	23.26	22.87
Catalyst					Wedge				
alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD	alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD
30	18.59	40.69	32.22	37.51	30	18.59	43.08	32.67	36.87
90	9.05	36.16	28.93	28.35	90	9.05	37.37	26.02	28.15
120	6.55	34.75	27.96	24.60	120	6.55	35.70	24.70	27.52
150	4.61	33.66	27.06	22.99	150	4.61	34.36	23.77	23.56
Round					Brine				
alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD	alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD
30	18.59	42.38	34.87	36.70	30	18.59	38.83	32.47	37.08
90	9.05	37.64	30.92	28.57	90	9.05	35.68	28.95	28.39
120	6.55	36.36	29.55	25.31	120	6.55	34.50	27.92	27.29
150	4.61	35.28	28.34	22.67	150	4.61	33.48	26.99	23.96

Table 3. **FPSNR (dB) comparison of different approaches.** Note that the noisy data is generated with the same random initialization and PSNR values are averaged.

Particle					Electrode				
alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD	alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD
30	8.19	19.82	14.36	14.45	30	9.90	33.84	20.97	25.61
90	6.72	16.31	11.75	10.89	90	7.18	26.81	17.89	14.91
120	6.51	15.11	11.09	10.78	120	6.80	25.17	16.57	15.94
150	6.38	14.87	10.53	9.59	150	6.57	23.57	15.37	12.46
Catalyst					Wedge				
alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD	alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD
30	12.67	37.50	28.34	29.56	30	10.73	35.08	23.77	24.72
90	8.48	31.43	22.49	20.47	90	7.57	28.30	18.64	16.98
120	7.80	29.93	20.74	17.04	120	7.11	26.68	17.18	16.64
150	7.39	28.25	19.38	16.11	150	6.81	25.05	16.02	13.89
Round					Brine				
alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD	alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD
30	10.61	34.49	25.13	23.52	30	14.40	39.26	20.72	31.91
90	7.55	27.65	18.95	16.91	90	9.40	33.84	24.84	23.39
120	7.09	25.98	17.35	14.44	120	8.54	32.44	23.12	22.30
150	6.81	24.39	16.11	13.11	150	8.00	30.71	21.71	19.52

Table 4. **PPSNR (dB) comparison of different approaches.** The best results are shown in boldface.

C.4. Results of real dataset

The raw projection image is noisy. After applying the proposed SUM algorithm to the raw data, we can clearly see the morphological structure of NCM particles. This improvement is more obvious for the low energy ranges.

Particle					Electrode				
alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD	alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD
30	0.29	0.98	0.89	0.97	30	0.16	0.98	0.72	0.97
90	0.08	0.96	0.59	0.66	90	0.05	0.93	0.60	0.43
120	0.05	0.95	0.50	0.58	120	0.03	0.92	0.45	0.48
150	0.05	0.94	0.44	0.44	150	0.03	0.90	0.35	0.29
Catalyst					Wedge				
alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD	alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD
30	0.35	0.98	0.91	0.99	30	0.18	0.98	0.80	0.96
90	0.09	0.97	0.76	0.77	90	0.06	0.95	0.59	0.55
120	0.08	0.96	0.65	0.59	120	0.06	0.93	0.45	0.50
150	0.06	0.95	0.55	0.56	150	0.04	0.91	0.37	0.33
Round					Brine				
alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD	alpha	Noisy	SUM	BM4D	SVD
30	0.29	0.98	0.90	0.98	30	0.54	0.98	0.93	0.99
90	0.09	0.96	0.74	0.78	90	0.12	0.98	0.86	0.95
120	0.07	0.95	0.62	0.56	120	0.09	0.97	0.83	0.90
150	0.06	0.94	0.52	0.48	150	0.08	0.96	0.80	0.88

Table 5. Correlation comparison of different approaches. The best results within a 0.3 margin are shown in boldface.

Figure 12. Results of real dataset. (a) The average spectrum after denoising before normalization. (b) Typical frames under different energies before and after denoising.

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